

BC-SIM-TR-007 STC ICO5 REPORT

Issue 1.0

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Change Log

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope

The present document has been issued to describe the 5yh Instrument CheckOut Phase Tests of STC, channel of the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYSTEM (SIMBIO-SYS).

1.2. Reference Document

- [RD. 1] BC-SIM-TN-003_-_Reports_and_Note_Layout_and_Flow, [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/36](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/36)
- [RD. 2] BC-SIM-GAF-MA-002 rev.8_SIMBIO-SYS FM User Manual, 2017
- [RD. 3] BC-SIM-TR-040 EGSE ICO#5 Report ([10.5281/zenodo.11236096](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236096))
- [RD. 4] BC-SIM-TR-003 - STC NECP Report ([10.20371/INAF/TechRep/26](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/26))
- [RD. 5] BC-SIM-PL-008_-_SIMBIO-SYS_Checkout_05_Test_Summary ([10.5281/zenodo.11208000](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11208000))
- [RD. 6] BC-SIM-TR-007 STC Delta-NECP REPORT ([10.20371/INAF/TechRep/71](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/71))
- [RD. 7] BC-SIM-TR-031_-_STC_ICO#04_report ([10.20371/INAF/TechRep/208](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/208))
- [RD. 8] BC-SIM-TN-008_-_SIMBIO-SYS_FOP update after ICO#02 ([10.20371/INAF/TechRep/162](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/162))
- [RD. 9] SIMIONI, E., et al. CMOS detectors: lessons learned during the STC stereo channel preflight calibration. In: International Conference on Space Optics—ICSO 2016. International Society for Optics and Photonics, 2017. p. 105622M
- [RD. 10] BC-SIM-TR-026_-_STC_ICO#03_report ([10.20371/INAF/TechRep/186](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/186))
- [RD. 11] BC-SIM-TR-019 -STC ICO2 Report ([10.20371/INAF/TechRep/138](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/138))
- [RD. 12] BC-SIM-TR-018_-_HRIC ICO2 Report ([10.20371/INAF/TechRep/100](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/100))
- [RD. 13] BC-SIM-TR-028_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#03_Interchannel_TR ([10.20371/INAF/TechRep/197](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/197))
- [RD. 14] BC-SIM-TR-034_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#04_Interchannel_TR ([10.5281/zenodo.8366159](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8366159))
- [RD. 15] BC-SIM-TR-038_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO4b_Interchannel_TR ([10.5281/zenodo.10649964](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10649964))
- [RD. 16] BC-SIM-TR-010_-_SIMBIO-SYS Instrument delta NECP Test Report ([10.20371/INAF/TechRep/83](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/83))

1.3.Acronyms

ACK	Acknowledgment
ADC	Analogical Digit Converter
APID	Application Process IDentifier
ASW	Application SoftWare
CM	Color Mode
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DSNU	Dark Signal not Uniformity
FOP	Flight Operation Procedure
FPA	Focal Plane Assembly
HK	Housekeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
ICO	Instrument Checkout
IT	Integration Time
ME	Main Electronics
NECP	Near Earth Commissioning Phase
OBCP	On-Board Control Procedure
OB	Optical Bench
OBSW	On Board Software
PDOR	Payload Direct Operation Request
PDS	Planetary Data System
PE	Proximity Electronics
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PSC	Packet Sequence Control
RT	Repetition Time
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem
SSC	Source Sequence Count
SSMM	Solid State Mass Memory
STC	STereo imaging Channel
S/C	Space-Craft
TC	TeleCommand
TEC	Thermo-Electric Cooler
TM	Telemetry
VIHI	Visible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

1.4. Document Format and Repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [[RD. 1] and will be archived on the SIMBIO-SYS ZENODO community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=SIMBIO-SYS>), on the INAF Open Access repository and the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

1.5. Document Organization

This document is organized in sections whose topics are listed as follows:

- Section 2 – Definitions and assumptions
- Section 3 – ICO5 objectives, with a brief description of the test executed.
- Section 4 – “Functional test” description including commanding and HK interpretation and discussion.
- Section 5 – “Performance Test” description including commanding and HK interpretation and discussion.
- Section 6 – “Low Frequency Behavior Test” description including commanding and HK interpretation and discussion.
- Section 7 – “Interference test” high level description.
- Section 8 – Description of the test reports in attachment to Section 9.
- Section 9 – Test reports collection.

2. Definitions and assumptions

In this section the main physical and technical terms are defined.

2.1. STC Sensors

Param.	Param. Name	Unit	Calibration
NSS21040	Temperature FPA1	K	CSSP0020TM
NSS21041	Temperature FPA2	K	CSSP0021TM
NSS21042	Temperature PE	K	CSSP0022TM
NSS21043	Temp FPA Package (channel fw)	K	CSSP0023TM
NSS21044	Temp Optical bench (channel bw)	K	CSSP0024TM
NSS21050	PE 3.3V Measured	V	CSSP0025TM
NSS21051	TEC Current	A	CSSP0026TM

Table 1 Main temperature sensors of STC on the FPA, PE, the backside of the detector and the STC OB as Reported in [RD. 2]. All HK belong to "SIMB STC Housekeeping" Packet (YSS40001)

The position of the temperature sensors are shown in **Figure 1** (a,b) extracted by [RD. 2] .

The STC Temperature FPA1 and FPA2 sensors, hereafter abbreviated with TFPA1 and TFPA2 respectively, are located close to the detector surface. Their measures indicate an increase in the temperature when the detector is switched on and then a lowering after the TEC switching on; their temperature values are also used as a feedback for interpreting the TEC behavior.

The Temp Channel-FW sensor, defined as the Focal Plane Assembly (FPA) Package in EGSE [RD. 3], is located on the hot side of the FPA package, thus it is expected to have values corresponding to instrument temperature; the Temp Channel-BW sensor, defined as STC Optical Bench (OB) in EGSE [RD. 3] is located on the back side of one folding mirrors as in Figure 1 (b) and gives a measure of the OB temperature in the front part of the STC channel "Ch-Low".

Figure 1 In (a) the location of the "STC Temperature Channel-fw/FPA Package" (NSS21043) temperature sensor (red rectangle). As highlighted in the 3D CAD model (no pictures are available, it is not present in the original CAD model), this sensor is placed onto the FPA package, in the same position where the corresponding sensor is placed on the HRIC FPA. In (b) the location of the "STC Temperature Channel-bw/ STC Optical Bench" (NSS21044) temperature sensor, as shown in the 3D CAD model (no picture available).

More details on the Sensors positions are reported [RD. 4].

2.2. STC-ICO5 Tests

As reported in [RD. 5], the ICO5 SIMBIO-SYS Phase (2021-06-14) had the scope to verify the health status of the instrument at channel and system level after 30 months after NECP phase. Few functional and performance tests are planned to monitor the evolution of some key instrument parameters.

During Functional Tests, as performed in previous ICOs differently from NECP phase (see [RD. 4]), the switch on of the Channels was performed after the update of the optimized parameters (see [RD. 6]) for the gentle activation of the TEC (to avoid peak of the TEC current in the case of difference of temperature greater than 10K).

Table 2 reports the different phases of the ICO for STC channel.

Test name	Monitoring	UTC first Image
STC FUNCTIONAL TEST	PE, TEC, MEMORY, ACQUISITION, CAPABILITY	16:28:40.015151
STC Performance Test	DC Verification	16:45:00.017800
STC LFB	Low Frequency Behaviour	17:05:05.015519
Interference Test	Interference throw the three channels	18:15:31.017416

Table 2 Table of the Tests as reported in [RD. 3].

2.3. BepiColombo CF Sensors

This section shows the trend of the STC Cold Finger (CF) temperature sensor named MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-STC-CF and identified as MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-STC-CF by ESA (for more details see [RD. 6]) In this section we consider the temperature measured for the CF sensor defined in the previous section during the ICO5 tests (i.e., between 12:00 and 23:00 of 14/06/2021).

STC CF temperature is shown in **Figure 2**. HKs were acquired with a sample rate of 1 minute.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2 Measurement for STC CF during ICO5 phase. Temperature is reported in °C. On the right axis the status of the nominal (a) and redundant (b) heaters.

The on off cycles plotted in **Figure 2 (a)** are reported in **Figure 3** which shows for each time of the ICO5 test the duration between a switch on and off of the main heater. Duration initially measured around 8 minutes reaches 13 minutes at the end of the ICO when the temperature has reached the stabilization.

Figure 3 Cycle on-off duration during the ICO5 phase for the main heater (id HK: NPWD0923)

2.4.STC Functional Test

2.4.1. Test description

During ICO#05 the STC functionality has been verified by means of dedicated Functional Test procedures with the aim of verifying:

- o PE, TEC and detector activation
- o memory/registers status
- o science acquisition capability

The STC functionality will be tested by means of the following TCs sequence:

- PE switch-on
- Detector switch-on
- TEC switch-on (optimized TEC parameters)
- Test of the reading and writing of a specific memory address
- The following science acquisitions:
 - o a ten of GM compressed acquisitions with low RT,
 - o a ten of GM compressed acquisitions with high RT,
 - o a ten of CM compressed acquisitions with low RT,
 - o a ten of CM compressed acquisitions with high RT
 - o 250 of WinX compressed acquisitions with high RT=2s
- TEC switch-off
- Detector switch-off

- PE switch-off

As performed in ICO4 (see STC [RD. 7]) function tests did not command only the four TCs of TST-020 (see [RD. 8] for details) but includes a 5th TC (science 005) to have a measurement of the low frequency behavior with the other channel switched off. The commanded acquisition has a low IT (11 raw), a RT=2s and a IBR=8.

2.4.2. Commanding

During the switch on of the ME, before the beginning of the ICO4 and as performed before ICO3, the new parameters were updated substituting the nominal values with the optimized ones. Differently from other uploaded parameters (i.e. VIHI Bias Detector parameters which remain in the PE RAM until the PE is switched off) when the TEC parameters have been uploaded, they are written in the CPCU RAM, so they remain available up to the next SIMBIO-SYS switch off (see [RD. 2] Section 8.3.1.10 and 8.3.1.16).

The summary of the parameters used for STC in the two phases is reported in following table.

Name	Data-kind	Meaning	NECP Phase Nominal	ICO1 Phase
NP	[16 bit uint]	Proportional gain	77	128
NI	[16 bit uint]	integral gain	33	229
N_E	[16 bit uint] (only 12 lsb's may be not zero)	PI operation threshold	112 (10K)	34(3K)
NSS	[16 bit uint] (only 14 lsb's may be not zero)	Soft start Ramp slope	12289	5
BSS o BSTART	[2 bits]	- bit 15= 0/1 : anti- windup ON/OFF; - bit 14= 0/1 : P-only/ramp soft start	11	11
T_REF	[16 bit uint]	Reference FPA commanded temperature (only 12 lsb's may be not zero)	2799 (268 K)	2799 (268 K)

Table 3 TEC Soft-Start parameters

Once the ME was switched on (with the updated parameters) all the functional tests were commanded by a sequence of the FOP SS-TST-020 ([RD. 6]) **followed by a Science TC**. All science TCs planned were nominally executed. The summary of the TCs and the consequent images dataset generated is reported in **Table 4** and **Table 5**.

Timeline	Relative	TC	Scope	Notes
0:00:00	00:00:00	ZSS00329	Set HK to 1 s	
0:00:05	00:00:05	ZSS17210	Send SIMB STC Detector On/Off	Switch On STC PE (Channel) (to restore after ASW update with correct TEC initialization).
0:00:10	00:00:05	ZSS17203	Send SIMB STC Thermal Control On/Off	TEC set point: 268K

0:00:15	00:00:05	ZSS17206	Send SIMB STC Read Addr	Read memory present status
0:00:30	00:00:15	ZSS17206	Send SIMB STC Read Addr	
0:00:35	00:00:05	ZSS17207	Send SIMB STC Write Addr	Test Writing Memory
0:00:40	00:00:05	ZSS17204	Send SIMB STC Confirm Command	
0:00:45	00:00:05	ZSS17207	Send SIMB STC Write Addr	Test STC science test pattern
0:00:50	00:00:05	ZSS17204	Send SIMB STC Confirm Command	
0:15:50	00:15:00	ZSS17202	Start STC Science (GM Mean)	
0:16:10	00:00:20	ZSS17202	Start STC Science (GM Max)	
0:18:20	00:02:10	ZSS17202	Start STC Science (CM-Mean)	Science
0:18:30	00:00:10	ZSS17202	Start STC Science (CM-Max)	
0:18:54	00:00:24	ZSS17209	Send SIMB STC Stop Science	End test.
0:18:59	00:00:05	ZSS00329	Set HK to 10 s	

Table 4 Timeline of the Functional Tests with the references to the commanded ZSS (see[RD. 3] for more details).

The resulting database derived by EGSE telemetry to raw pipeline is reported in **Table 5**. All science TCs were in continuous mode.

EGSE_NT C	First_Acq	Duratio n	NAC Q	DimX	IT	RT	IBR	Window
[#]	[UTC]	[s]	[#]	[px]	[ms]	[s]		
1	16:28:40.015151Z	18	10	896	0.096	2	32	GM
2	16:29:00.015075Z	123	11	896	1.4976	12.3	32	GM
3	16:31:15.314833Z	4.4	12	896	5.2992	0.39999	63	CM
4	16:31:20.114821Z	22.5	12	896	37.7952	2.05	63	CM
5	16:32:50.014509Z	538	270	128	0.1056	2	8	Win-X

Table 5 Resulting database of the ICO4 Functional Test. All TCs were commanded with the CBD = 64x64

The four TCs of TST-020 (see [RD. 8]) were commanded respectively at 16:28:40, 16:29:00, 16:31:10 and 16:31:20 while the additive one at 16:32:50. Note that third one was executed with a delay of 5.3 sec as reported in the Timing Report in attachment in Section 10. This is due to the granularity of the ME in Science mode (for details see [RD. 6]).

2.4.3. HKs interpretation and discussion

No anomalies were detected for what concern temperatures (see **Figure 4**). TEC parameters updated allowed the “gentle” activation of the STC TEC introducing a graceful cooldown and so avoiding a possible OOL current peak as showed by **Figure 5b**.

Figure 4 The instrumental HK of STC for the Functional test of IC05.

(a)

Figure 5 PE measurement (a) and TEC current values (b) evolution over all the Tests of ICO5. For HK description details see **Table 1**.

2.4.4. Image Analysis

Science data acquired during Functional Tests has no anomalies from an operational point of view. A first reduction of the dataset is shown in **Figure 6**. The image shows, for each acquisition, the mean value of the windows included in the 4 TCs. Right y-axis (yellow) reports the distance between each acquisition and the previous one.

As expected for the firsts two TCs (GM) the signal results nominally constant for all the 3 windows considered (WINX+PANH+PANL). In the case of the CM the peak-issue (see [RD. 9]) brings to a not constant level of the dark in the case of high times between the acquisitions.

The issue will be resolved during the Scientific Phase of the Mission by mitigating the dark subtracting the mean value of the winx to the other windows acquired, guaranteeing to have a correct measurement of the dark both at the beginning or at the end of the acquisition sequences.

Figure 6 The figure reports the reduction in mean of the images of the TST-020 FCP (including the first 4 TC of the Functional tests. Right y-axis (yellow) reports the distance between each acquisition and the previous one

The TST-Results plotted in Figure 6 can be compared with the same plot provided in all the other ICOs (i.e. [RD. 10]). It is clear that the 3rd TC differently by the other test do not provide the same number of acquisitions because a short delay in between the execution by satellite and the acceptance by ME made the TC cross the limit of the previous RT (12.3s) and a delay of other 12.3s was introduced by ME.

Last TC of the functional test is shown in **Figure 7**. The TC is commended to have a test of the STC DC with a RT=2s without the interference of other channels. A carry wave with an amplitude of ± 10 DN and period of about 9 minutes min is highlighted by the test.

Figure 7 The figure reports the reduction in mean of the images of the 5th TC of the Functional tests of **ICO5**. Right y-axis (yellow) reports the distance between each acquisition and the previous one)

Same functional test was performed during ICO4. The same timeline underlined a different LFB (see Ref [RD. 7]) with a period of 2.37 min. For comparison we report here the same data reduction of the 5th TC of the functional test of ICO4 (see **Figure 8**).

As reported in following sections a strong difference in the environment status between ICO4 and ICO5 is due to the fact that during ICO5 both the heaters here used (details in Table 9).

Figure 8 The figure reports the reduction in mean of the images of the last TC of Functional test of **ICO4**. Right y-axis (yellow) reports the distance between each acquisition and the previous one

2.5. STC Performance Test

2.5.1. Test description

The Performance Test of ICO5 repeated the blooming test performed during ICO1 with different windows dimensions.

2.5.2. Commanding

This test has been performed through the execution of 1 pre-defined PDORs named:

- SIMBIOSYS_STC_ICO#05_Performance (SPOT ID: BPSS00840)

See [RD. 9] for more details.

The PDOR executes 4 different tests:

- the first and second tests are the DC measurement in GM with low and high RT (0.45 and 7) to verify the health of the FPA. Differently from the other ICOs the CT dimensions were set to 384 px to have a verification of the windowing effect.

- Third and fourth phases have the scope of evaluating the DC measurement on a specific region of the detector (hereafter called “Blooming”) for the same low and high RTs repeating the same acquisition performed in GM but changing the FPA region to be acquired. FPA “blooming” region considered is defined with a minimal dimension of 64x128 pixels covering the rows from 866 to 929 and strips from 22 to 23.

The timeline of the test is reported in **Table 6**.

EGSE NTCs	Fop Names	Mode	NTCs [#]	Min IT [ms]	Max It [ms]	RT [s]
1-7	ASSF307	GM	7	0	270	0.45
8-14	ASSF307	GM	7	0	270	7
15-21	ASSF300	Blooming+WinX	7	0	270	0.45
22-28	ASSF300	Blooming+WinX	7	0	270	7

Table 6 Timeline of the 4 phases TCs of the PERFORMANCE TEST with the references to the commanded FOPs (see [RD. 8] for more details). All phases command an acquisition mode with different Its (14 in the case of GM, 7 for the blooming window with low RT and 7 for the blooming window with hi RT).

The resulting database derived by EGSE telemetry to raw pipeline is reported in **Table 7**. Different colours are applied for the different tests (see **Table 2**) included in the ICO.

EGSE_NT C [#]	First_Acq [UTC]	Duration [s]	NACQ [#]	DimX [px]	IT [ms]	RT [s]	Windows
1	16:45:00.017800	4.05	10	384	0.0004	0.45	GM
2	16:45:07.017739	4.05	10	384	0.1056	0.45	GM
3	16:45:14.017892	4.05	10	384	0.192	0.45	GM
4	16:45:21.017770	4.05	10	384	0.288	0.45	GM
5	16:45:28.017770	4.05	10	384	0.96	0.45	GM
6	16:45:35.017785	4.05	10	384	2.4	0.45	GM
7	16:45:42.017724	4.05	10	384	270	0.45	GM
8	16:45:49.017769	63	10	384	0.0004	7	GM
9	16:47:01.017662	63	10	384	0.1056	7	GM
10	16:48:13.017418	63	10	384	0.192	7	GM
11	16:49:25.017188	63	10	384	0.288	7	GM
12	16:50:37.017127	63	10	384	0.96	7	GM
13	16:51:49.016959	63	10	384	2.4	7	GM
14	16:53:01.016958	63	10	384	270	7	GM
15	16:54:13.016744	4.05	10	128	0.0004	0.45	Blooming+Win-X
16	16:54:20.016668	4.05	10	128	0.1056	0.45	Blooming+Win-X
17	16:54:27.016759	4.05	10	128	0.192	0.45	Blooming+Win-X
18	16:54:34.016652	4.05	10	128	0.288	0.45	Blooming+Win-X
19	16:54:41.016652	4.05	10	128	0.96	0.45	Blooming+Win-X

20	16:54:48.016729	4.05	10	128	2.4	0.45	Blooming+Win-X
21	16:54:55.016729	4.05	10	128	270	0.45	Blooming+Win-X
22	16:55:02.016637	63	10	128	0.0004	7	Blooming+Win-X
23	16:56:14.016499	63	10	128	0.1056	7	Blooming+Win-X
24	16:57:26.016300	63	10	128	0.192	7	Blooming+Win-X
25	16:58:38.016178	63	10	128	0.288	7	Blooming+Win-X
26	16:59:50.016147	63	10	128	0.96	7	Blooming+Win-X
27	17:01:02.015887	63	10	128	2.4	7	Blooming+Win-X
28	17:02:14.015734	63	10	128	270	7	Blooming+Win-X

Table 7 Database derived by EGSE. All TCs (dated 2020-06-14) commanded CBD=64x64 and IBR=1.

2.5.3. HKs interpretation and discussion

No anomaly was revealed.

2.5.4. Image Analysis

The mean reduction of all the Performance test is reported in **Figure 9**.

Figure 9 The figure reports the reduction in mean of the images of the Functional tests. Right y-axis (yellow) reports the distance between each acquisition and the previous one.

Considering that the test repeats two times the same IT and RT series acquiring in the first case the GM and in the second the Blooming windows a comparison can be done in **Figure 10** where the GM is shown in red and the Blooming acquisition in green.

Figure 10 The figure reports the reduction in mean of the images of the Functional tests. Right y-axis (yellow) reports the distance between each acquisition and the previous one.

2.6. LFB Test

2.6.1. Test description

Part of the tests described has the scope of measuring the Low Frequency Behavior of STC as function of the Channels Status and Repetition Time formal parameter.

2.6.2. Commanding

With the same goal (measure the effect of the RT on the single acquisitions of STC) three TC were commanded to investigate the RT=0.8,7,12.3s nominal limits of the RT to be commendable.

EGSE_NT C	First_Acq	Duratio n	NAC Q	DimX	IT	RT
[#]	[UTC]	[s]	[#]	[px]	[ms]	[s]
1	17:05:05.015519Z	419	525	128	0.1056	0.8
2	17:12:05.014800Z	413	60	128	0.1056	7
3	17:19:05.014019Z	418	35	128	0.1056	12.3

Table 8 Database derived by EGSE. All TCs (dated 2020-06-14) commanded the acquisition of Win-X with CBD=64x64 and IBR=8 to ensure minimal DV.

2.6.3. HKs interpretation and discussion

As shown in **Figure 7** STC is affected by a LFB with a period of about 9 minutes at the end of Functional test where the RT was commanded to 2 sec for a duration of 537s which represent the 9 minutes of phenomena behavior. Different is the behavior of the LFB well reported in **Figure 11**.

Figure 11 The figure reports the mean of each acquisition (in blue left y-axis) of the three TCs the LFB Test. Right y-axis (yellow) report the distance between each acquisition and the previous one)

Short time of the experiment (based on the assumption of a period around 2 minutes) do not allow to measure with high precision the carrier wave of the LFB which can be considered around 15 minutes.

A summary of the LFB measurement is reported in following table.

ICO	Test Name	RT [s]	Period [min]	Note	TPE	Heater 1	Heater 2	CF Stabilization duration
ICO3	Interference	2	2.62	With HRIC	286-288	6min	On	8 min
ICO4	Functional	2	2.37	Alone	278.9	On	Off	Non in temp
ICO4	Interference	2	1.56	With HRIC	281.6	On	Off	Non in temp
ICO4	Interference	1	1.7	With HRIC	283.7	On	Off	Non in temp
ICO4	Interference	2	1.87	With HRIC	284.9	On	Off	Non in temp
ICO4	Interference	1	1.9	With HRIC	285.6	On	Off	Non in temp

ICO4 b	Interference	1	2.56	With HRIC/VIHI	285.9	On	Off	7 min
ICO4 b	Interference	1	2.18	With HRIC/VIHI	288.2	On	Off	7 min
ICO5	Functional	2	9	Alone	286	On	7 min	15 min
ICO5	LFB	0.8,7 And 12.3	15?	Alone	288.4	On	7.6 min	15 min
ICO5	Interference	1.5	2.68	With VIHI	285.7- 288.5	On	9 min	11.6 min
ICO5	Interference	1	2.6	With HRIC	287-289	On	10.3 min	10 min

Table 9 Table reporting for all the previous ICOs the conditions of the tests linked to LBF behavior and its period

3. Interference test

3.1. Test description

The aim of the test is the monitoring of low frequency behaviour (see [RD. 11] for STC and [RD. 12] for HRIC channel) and the impact of the parallel HRIC acquisitions on this effect.

Previous analysis showed a carrier wave with an amplitude of 6DN and a period of 3 minutes on the mean signal of the STC and HRIC acquisitions.

The interference between the two channels have minimal impact on the DC (both comparable with the RON). In any case the effect is uniform on the FPA which means that the DC mitigation applied during images calibration will remove this bias without effect on the performances.

This phenomenon, measured for STC during the Orbit test (see [RD. 6]) required additive tests during ICO3 (see [RD. 13]) including the two imaging Channels and during ICO4 (see [RD. 14])and ICO4b(see [RD. 15]) including even VIHI channel.

The mutual interference between the three channel was verified during ICO5.

For more details, see following dedicated Interchannel Test Report.

4. Reports

In this section attached reports are described. They trace the HKs and the main fast reduction of all the acquisitions (Performance Reports).

4.1. Performance report

From the xml files (attached to this report), a table-format report (for more details see [RD. 16]) has been derived that contains the following listed quantities:

Column	Name	Description
A	ACQ NUM	Number of the acquisition science the first on of the test
B	TC	ID of the TC corresponding to the folder in simbio server (i.e. science001)
C	last_image	Boolean flag defining if the acquisition is or not the last of the TC considered.
D	start_obs	UTC time of the acquisition
E-J	name_WX	Names of the windows acquired as reported in the xml files.
K	start_obs_et_[s]	UTC time of the in seconds
L	IT_[s]	Integration time of the WIN1 acquisition as reported in xml files.It correspond to the Integration time (IT) for each image acquired for a specific telecommand
M	RT_mean_[s]	Repetition time evaluated as the mean time between the first and last acquisition of the TC. In case of 1 acquisition it is not evaluated.
N	WT_[s]	Waiting Time of an acquisition. Derived by the time distance since and the previous acquisition (even if associate to another TC).
O-S	TXXXX_[K]	Temperature HKs (FPA1, FPA2, Channel1, Channel2 and PE temperature) as reported in the xml file
T-AK	mean_Wx_[DN]	For each window acquired is reported the mean of the windows in DN.
	mean64_Wx_[DN]	For each window acquired is reported the mean of the last 64 column of the window in DN.

	DSNU_Wx	For each window acquired is the standard deviation (Dark Signal Non Uniformity (DSNU)) of the window in DN.
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Table 10 Columns description of the Performance Report file

4.2.Attached documents

In this section the attached documents are listed with the corresponding links.

Section	Description	Name Report	Link
4	Functional Test	04_-_STC_Functional_Test_20240519.xlsx	
5	Performance Test	05_-_STC_Performance_Test_20240519.xlsx	
6	LFB Test	06_-_STC_LFBTest_20240519.xlsx	

Table 11 Performance report file attachment covering the period including ICO5. The Log file is divided in sheets as EGSE structure in four different folder representing the different test..